

APPLYING FINITE ELEMENT COMPUTATIONS FOR THE DETERMINATION OF TRANSVERSE SHEAR MODULI OF HONEYCOMB CORES

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ABSTRACT

One of the most important properties of honeycomb cores for use in composite sandwich panels is the transverse shear stiffness which is governed by two independent shear moduli, G_{xz} and G_{yz} . Theoretical considerations on the cellular structure of honeycombs can be used to estimate directly G_{yz} . On the other hand, only bounds can be found for G_{xz} . The aim of this paper is to provide an accurate estimation of G_{xz} through finite element calculations. It is shown that this modulus depends on the thickness of the core and an empirical formula giving this shear modulus as a function of the core thickness is provided.

Keywords : honeycomb cores, sandwich panels, transverse shear moduli

1. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of the transverse shear properties of honeycomb cores is essential for the design of sandwich panels. Within the framework of elasticity, it is easy to show that two independent transverse shear moduli govern the out-of-plane shear behaviour of a honeycomb [1] : G_{xz} and G_{yz} (Figure 1). These two shear moduli can be estimated using two approaches.

The first way is to perform conventional shear tests : three-point bending tests or rail-shear tests. However, both of them feature specific difficulties that give rise to some discrepancies between estimated and measured moduli [2] [3]. For instance, local bending of the faces or crushing of the core occurs during a three-point bending test. Free boundaries also induce perturbations during the rail shear test.

Another approach is to compute the moduli using theoretical considerations on the cellular structure of the honeycomb [1] [4] [5]. However, these methods are based on the assumption that the walls that constitute the honeycomb are under pure shear stress when the honeycomb is sheared. This assumption is satisfied only for a shear loading in the y direction. Hence, only G_{yz} can be calculated analytically. For any other shearing direction, the shear stress in the wall is not uniform; as a result, only analytical bounds can be found for the second shear modulus G_{xz} .

The aim of this paper is to compute the shear modulus G_{xz} using finite element calculations performed on a unit cell which is representative of the whole honeycomb. It will be shown that the

shear modulus depends on the thickness of the honeycomb. A formula that gives the shear modulus as a function of the thickness will be provided. Finally, the shear stress contour in the walls inside the honeycomb will be presented and shear stress concentrations in the vicinity of the skins will be pointed out.

Figure 1. Geometry of the honeycomb.

2. ANALYSIS

A honeycomb can be considered as an interconnected network of walls which are the faces of the cells (Figure 1). This typical aspect has been used by Kelsey et al. [4], Penzien and Didriksson [6] and more recently by Gibson et al. [5] who considered the deformation of a basic cell under different loading to provide the honeycomb stiffnesses as a function of its geometry.

It must be clearly emphasized that these stiffnesses are assessed assuming a uniform stress distribution in the walls of the structure. Unfortunately, the actual stress distribution in the walls of a sheared honeycomb is not uniform and remains unknown in the general case. Hence, only lower and upper bounds of the shear modulus can be computed in a given direction. Those two bounds are equal in the y direction for any geometry of the cell. They are also equal in any direction for regular hexagonal cells with walls of equal thickness ($t=t'$). Moreover, in this latter case, the honeycomb can be considered as an equivalent isotropic material in the (x,y) plane whereas it is orthotropic in all other cases. On the other hand, usual regular hexagonal honeycomb made from metal foil are characterized by $t'=2t$ and are therefore not isotropic in the (x,y) plane. The two bounds for G_{xz} are different in this latter case. They are obtained using the theorem of minimum potential energy and the theorem of minimum complementary energy. The first theorem gives an upper bound using a kinematically compatible uniform strain field; the second one gives a lower bound using a statically compatible uniform stress field. The following results are directly quoted from Kelsey et al. [4].

Let us consider the part of honeycomb depicted in Figure 1. It is characterised by four dimensionless aspect ratios

$$R_1 = \frac{t}{b} \quad R_2 = \frac{a}{b} \quad R_3 = \frac{h}{a} \quad R_4 = \frac{t'}{t} \quad (1)$$

where h is the thickness of the core.

For usual honeycomb cores obtained with the corrugated or the expansion process [7], $R_4 = 2$ and the shear moduli in directions x and y are

$$\frac{1+R_2\sin\theta}{R_2(1+R_2)\cos\theta} R_1 G \leq G_{xz} \leq \frac{1+R_2\sin^2\theta}{(1+R_2\sin\theta)R_2\cos\theta} R_1 G \quad (2)$$

$$G_{yz} = \frac{\cos\theta}{1+R_2\sin\theta} R_1 G \quad (3)$$

where G is the shear modulus of the constitutive foil material.

For walls of equal length (i. e. $R_2 = 1$), the maximum difference between the two bounds of G_{xz} is obtained for $\theta = 0$. Such a cell geometry can be obtained with overexpanded honeycombs. Equation (2) reduces to

$$\frac{R_1}{2} G \leq G_{xz} \leq R_1 G \quad (4)$$

Using this approach, the shear modulus G_{xz} , which is one of the most important mechanical parameters of honeycombs, is predicted with a maximum uncertainty of 100 % in the first case for walls of equal length ($R_2 = 1$). Such a difference is due to the fact that the actual shear stress field is unknown. It can be noted that the aspect ratio R_3 is not taken into account whereas shear tests provide shear moduli that depend on the thickness of the core [3].

3. CALCULATION OF G_{xz}

The goal is here to compute the shear stress field in the cell walls and to deduce the value of the shear modulus G_{xz} . Modeling a whole honeycomb for a finite element analysis cannot reasonably be considered because of the high complexity of such a structure. The model would have too many degrees of freedom to be studied with usual finite element programmes. Hence, only a small relevant part of the honeycomb is studied here using a homogenization approach. This part is called unit cell in the following. Obviously it must be chosen in such a way that it is representative of the whole honeycomb. This unit cell is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Unit cell.

The unit cell is built up with one quarter of one central wall and one quarter of one inclined wall. This reduction of the size of the cell to be studied is due to the different symmetries in the

honeycomb. For the calculation of G_{xz} , the top face of the honeycomb is subjected to a uniform displacement U along x direction while the bottom face remains fixed. Thanks to the symmetry, the horizontal displacement of centre line CL 1 is $\frac{U}{2}$. Hence, the relative displacement between the top face and CL 1 is $\frac{U}{2}$. The other displacements along the boundary can easily be found with similar considerations. For instance, the vertical displacements of corners I and II are unlike [8]. For symmetry reason, the vertical displacement along CL 2 and CL 3 is therefore zero; the displacement of corner I along the y direction is also zero. Note that the thickness of the central wall is divided by 2 thanks to the symmetry of honeycomb about the x direction. Full details concerning the boundary conditions used for the calculation of G_{xz} can be found in [8]. It must be pointed out that rotations along CL 1, CL 2 and CL 3 are free. On the other hand, rotations along the two lines of the top face could be restrained or free. The reality is between these two cases. However, it has been observed that this type of boundary condition only has a little influence on the calculated shear modulus G_{xz} [8]. Hence, restrained rotations are used in the following.

The equivalent shear modulus is deduced using the following method. The cell is subjected to an equivalent shear strain γ_{equ} such that

$$\gamma_{equ} = \frac{U}{h} \quad (5)$$

The force to be applied to shear the unit cell is one quarter of the force to be applied to shear one hexagonal block of equivalent homogeneous material. The equivalent shear stress is computed firstly by adding the magnitude of the forces which have been applied on the top face of the unit cell to obtain the displacement U . The global resulting force is F . The forces on these two lines are necessary to shear one quarter of the hexagon depicted in Figure 1 which area is

$$S = 2a \cos\theta (b+a \sin\theta) \quad (6)$$

The equivalent shear stress τ_{equ} is then obtained from F and S

$$\tau_{equ} = \frac{4F}{S} \quad (7)$$

The equivalent shear modulus G_{xz} is finally

$$G_{xz} = \frac{\tau_{equ}}{\gamma_{equ}} \quad (8)$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Mesh of the unit cell

Simulations have been carried out using 4-noded quadrilateral plate elements formulated in the three-dimensional space. The nodes have five degrees of freedom : three translation and the usual two rotations that produce out-of-plane bending. The material characteristics are $E = 72 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu = 0.31$. The mesh of the walls of the unit cell is such that each wall has four elements along the x direction. The number of elements along the z direction is such that the elements have a square shape. It has been checked through a convergence study that the present mesh provides a very accurate value of F .

4.2. Calculation of G_{xz}

Several cell geometries defined by $0 \text{ deg} \leq \theta \leq 30 \text{ deg}$ and $1 \leq R_3 \leq 10$ have been studied. The two usual limits for cell angles $\theta = 30 \text{ deg}$ and $\theta = 0 \text{ deg}$ are reported in Figures 3 and 4 for different values of the aspect ratio R_3 . The two bounds obtained with equation (2) are also reported.

Figure 3. Shear modulus G_{xz} vs. aspect ratio R_3 , $\theta = 30 \text{ deg}$.

Figure 4. Shear modulus G_{xz} vs. aspect ratio R_3 , $\theta = 0 \text{ deg}$.

As may be seen, the shear modulus G_{xz} decreases as the aspect ratio R_3 decreases and tends to be equal to the lower bound. Moreover, the difference between the two bounds increases as the cell angle θ decreases. The influence of the thickness is therefore more sensitive for $\theta = 0$ deg. This point clearly shows that the shear modulus is a parameter that represents the global response of the structure : it cannot be considered as an intrinsic parameter that could characterize the core for any thickness.

The influence of the thickness can be taken into account using the following empirical formula which has been obtained from 30 different cell geometries studied with finite element calculations [8] :

$$G_{xz} = G_{xz}^{\text{lower}} + \frac{0.787}{R_3} (G_{xz}^{\text{higher}} - G_{xz}^{\text{lower}}) \quad (9)$$

where G_{xz}^{higher} and G_{xz}^{lower} are respectively the upper and lower bounds in equation (2). This relation can be considered as a good approximation of the shear modulus for $R_3 \geq 1$. This function is plotted in Figures 3 and 4 and it can be seen that the curves are in agreement with the points obtained with the finite element calculations.

4.3. Shear stress contour in the honeycomb walls

The influence of the thickness can be explained with the shear stress distribution in the walls of the honeycomb. It can be shown that a uniform shear stress distribution in the walls would induce a rotation of top and bottom faces of the honeycomb [8]. This rotation is obviously not compatible with the bonding of the skins onto the core. The shear stress field is therefore not uniform near the skins. It can be shown that these perturbations depends on the angle cell θ as well as on the thickness of the core [8]. This latter point is important : it is the reason why the shear modulus G_{xz} depends on the thickness on the core. For thin honeycombs, the shear stress field is completely heterogeneous in the walls. On the other hand, the shear stress tends to be uniform in the middle part of the walls for thicker cores. As a results, the shear modulus G_{xz} tends to be equal to the lower bound in equation (2) when the thickness of the core increases, because this bound is computed assuming a uniform shear stress distribution in the walls.

The influence of the skins is illustrated in a particular case in Figure 5, where the shear stress contours in both the central and the inclined walls of the unit cell are reported. In the present simulation, the angle cell is $\theta = 0$ deg, the aspect ratio is $R_3 = 6$ and the equivalent shear strain is $\gamma_{\text{equ}} = 10^{-2}$. The bonding of the skins induces perturbations in the shear stress field. Near the skin, the shear stress increases in the central wall and decreases in the inclined wall. However, the shear stress tends to be uniform in the middle part of the core. If both top and bottom faces of the core could freely rotate, the shear strain in the walls would be uniform and equal to 137 MPa [8]. As may be seen in Figure 5, the shear stress in the middle part of the walls is about uniform and slightly higher (between 143 MPa and 154 MPa) when the faces cannot rotate. Other simulations have shown that the shear stress tends to be equal to 137 MPa in the middle part of the walls when the thickness of the core increases. In conclusion, the influence of the skins can be regarded as a Saint-Venant effect which cannot be neglected for thin cores and which vanishes when the aspect ratio increases.

Conclusion

Finite element simulations performed on a relevant unit cell allow the accurate calculation of the transverse shear modulus G_{xz} of honeycomb cores as well as the shear stress field in the walls. It

has been shown that this modulus strongly depends on the aspect ratio of the cell and a formula providing this modulus for thin honeycombs is given. This approach could also be applied to other shapes of cells, like those described by Marshall [7].

Figure 5. Shear stress contour in the walls of the studied model, $\theta=0$ deg, $R_3 = 6$.

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